

Case Report

Jejunal diverticula presenting with small bowel volvulus and perforations: A rare life threatening complication

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ABSTRACT:

Jejunal diverticula are uncommon and may lead to complications like inflammation, perforation, and peritonitis. Small bowel volvulus (SBV), characterized by the twisting of the small intestine around its mesentery, can result in obstruction and strangulation. The coexistence of jejunal diverticula with SBV is a rare and potentially fatal condition.

Case Presentation:

A 60-year-old male presented with a four-day history of abdominal pain, distension, and non-passage of feces and flatus. He had a history of chronic smoking and alcohol use but no significant past medical or surgical history. Imaging studies indicated jejunal volvulus with dilated bowel loops, without signs of ischemia. Exploratory laparotomy revealed SBV with multiple jejunal diverticula located 25 cm, 35 cm, and 100 cm distal to the ligament of Treitz, with perforations in the latter two. Ischemia was noted in the terminal ileum and ileocecal junction. Surgical intervention included segmental jejunal resection with primary anastomosis and limited right hemicolectomy with end ileostomy and distal mucus fistula. The patient succumbed to sepsis on the fifteenth postoperative day.

Conclusion:

Jejunal diverticula complicated by SBV and perforation represent a rare, life-threatening scenario. Prompt diagnosis and urgent surgical management are essential for improving patient outcomes.

Keywords: *Jejunal diverticula, small bowel volvulus, perforation, peritonitis, sepsis*

INTRODUCTION:

Jejunal diverticulosis is a rare condition, with a reported prevalence of 0.3%–2.3%, predominantly affecting elderly individuals [1]. It is characterized by false diverticula herniations of the mucosal and submucosal layers through the muscularis propria most commonly located on the mesenteric side of the jejunum [2]. The aetiology is thought to involve chronic segmental dysmotility, increased intraluminal pressure, and focal weakening of the bowel wall at sites where mesenteric vessels penetrate [3]. Although typically asymptomatic, complications such as perforation, haemorrhage, obstruction, and small bowel volvulus (SBV) may occur in up to 6% of cases [4,5].

SBV is an uncommon but potentially life-threatening condition involving torsion of the bowel and mesentery, leading to obstruction and vascular compromise [6]. It is rare in adults but can occur

secondary to anatomical abnormalities, previous surgeries, adhesions, or bowel pathologies such as diverticulosis [7,8]. The condition is more prevalent in certain geographic areas, particularly parts of Asia and Africa, where dietary and genetic factors may increase susceptibility [9].

This report presents a rare case of jejunal diverticulosis complicated by volvulus, ischemia, and perforation, managed surgically but culminating in postoperative mortality, highlighting the serious implications of this condition in elderly patients.

Case Presentation:

A 60-year-old male presented with a four-day history of non-passage of faeces and flatus, accompanied by abdominal distension. He developed generalized abdominal pain over the past two days. The patient had a history of painless and altered rectal bleeding for five

years and was chronic smoker and alcoholic. He had no other significant medical or surgical history. On physical examination, the abdomen was distended but non-tender, with increased bowel sounds. Per rectal examination was unremarkable. Laboratory investigations revealed deranged serum electrolytes (Na:152mEq/L; K:>6.5mEq/L) and renal function tests (Urea:102mg/dl; Creatinine:2.0mg/dl). X-Ray abdomen showed dilated small bowel loops with air fluid levels. (Fig.1) A contrast-enhanced computed tomography (CT) scan showed twisting of a segment of the jejunum around its mesentery, with significant proximal bowel dilatation measuring approximately 4.2 cm. However, no signs of bowel ischemia were detected. (Fig. 2) Following adequate resuscitation, the patient underwent an exploratory laparotomy. Intraoperatively, twisting of small bowel was observed 5 cm proximal to the ileocecal junction (ICJ), with ischemic changes noted in the terminal ileum involving ICJ (Fig. 3 & 4).

Inter-bowel adhesions were present. Multiple jejunal diverticulum were identified at 25 cm, 35 cm, and 100 cm distal to the ligament of Treitz, with tiny perforations noted at 35 cm and 100 cm. Given the findings, a right limited hemicolectomy with segmental jejunal resection was performed, followed by a end-to-end anastomosis and end ileostomy with distal mucus fistula done. Post-operatively, the patient remained stable during the first week. His stoma was functional, and his general condition initially improved. However, in the second week, he developed signs of sepsis, including fever, tachycardia, and worsening abdominal pain. Examination revealed surgical site infection, which later progressed to wound dehiscence and burst abdomen. Despite aggressive resuscitation and broad-spectrum antibiotics, his condition deteriorated further and patient expired on fifteen postoperative day.

Figure 1: CT scan showing whirl sign

Figure 2: Green line indicates diverticulum with multiple perforations; yellow line indicates adhesions and site of volvulus and blue line indicates ileocecal junction(ICJ)

Figure3: Showing midgut volvulus with jejunal diverticular perforation: green line indicates ischemic changes at terminal ileum and blue line indicates jejunal diverticulum with perforation

DISCUSSION:

Jejunal diverticulosis is often an incidental finding, but in rare cases, it can present with life-threatening complications, as demonstrated in this case. The pathophysiology involves chronic dysmotility and elevated intraluminal pressure, which weaken the intestinal wall and predispose to diverticulum formation [3]. While generally benign, complications

can include bleeding, bacterial overgrowth, diverticulitis, perforation, and, more rarely, small bowel volvulus (SBV) [4,5].

SBV in adults is a surgical emergency characterized by torsion of the bowel around its mesentery, leading to mechanical obstruction and vascular compromise. Although congenital causes predominate in neonates, in adults, volvulus is often secondary to adhesions,

malrotation, long mesenteric attachments, or acquired pathology such as jejunal diverticulosis [6,7]. Diverticulosis may predispose to volvulus by creating structurally vulnerable segments due to chronic segmental stasis and altered motility [9].

In stable or subacute cases, diagnosis can be aided by small bowel follow-through, enteroclysis, capsule endoscopy, or double-balloon enteroscopy—especially in patients with nonspecific abdominal complaints or obscure gastrointestinal bleeding [10,11]. However, in acute presentations with suspected complications, CECT is the most effective imaging modality. It allows identification of diverticula, mesenteric swirl (the “whirl sign”), pneumoperitoneum, and signs of ischemia [12,13]. Nevertheless, early ischemic changes may be subtle or missed, emphasizing the importance of clinical vigilance and timely surgical exploration.

In the presented case, surgical intervention revealed multiple jejunal diverticula, two of which were perforated, with associated ischemia of the terminal ileum and ileocecal junction. Dense adhesions further distorted anatomical planes, limiting the feasibility of bowel preservation and necessitating a limited right hemicolectomy and segmental jejunal resection, followed by a end-to-end anastomosis and end ileostomy.

Despite initial postoperative stabilization, the patient died on postoperative day fifteen. Contributing factors likely included septic peritonitis from diverticular perforation, advanced age, extensive bowel resection, and systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS) progressing to multiorgan dysfunction syndrome (MODS) [14–16].

CONCLUSION:

This case underscores the importance of early recognition and intervention in jejunal diverticulosis with complications. Elderly patients with this condition are at higher risk for adverse outcomes due to comorbidities and reduced physiological reserve. Prompt imaging, surgical decision-making, and intensive postoperative care are critical in improving survival in such high-risk scenarios.

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